

'Living Next to the Port' online survey (methodology and process)

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Abstract

The article briefly describes online survey (methodology, process and data collected) conducted within the research project 'Living Next to the Port: Eco-narratives, Local Histories, and Environmental Activism in the Daugava Delta' carried out by researchers of Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia. The target group of the project is the residents of five neighborhoods of the Riga city port, but the aim is to study their attitude towards their place of residence, mainly focusing on various environmental and social aspects. The general approach of the study is of the descriptive-explanatory type and designed as participatory research, with the aim to actively involve residents in the design process. The study does not put forward quantifiable hypotheses. The survey was used in the study alongside other data collection methods, such as semi-structured interviews, expert interviews, observation and others. It was implemented in 2019.

Keywords: online survey, environmental sociology, environmental humanities, non-probability survey, survey methodology

1. About the study 'Living Next to the Port'

The research project 'Living Next to the Port: Eco-narratives, Local Histories, and Environmental Activism in the Daugava Delta' (2018-2021) is carried out by five researchers of [Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia](#) and led by Dr.Philol. Dace Bula. This is an interdisciplinary study of a group of researchers in the humanities, environmental and social sciences, whose ambition is to start the development of environmental humanities in Latvia, as well as to kickstart environmental sociology, which has not been established in Latvia so far (Zīle-Veisberga & Daugavietis, 2019). Dace Bula specializes in narrative research, Dr.Philol. Ieva Garda studies life stories, MAnth Agita Pusvilka studies environmental activism, Dr.Geogr. Kristīne Āboliņa is an environmental scientist, MSc Agnese Zīle-Veisberga and Dr.Soc. Jānis Daugavietis are sociologists.

The most general research question of 'Living Next to the Port' is this: how do today's residents experience and feel life in the Daugava delta and in the neighborhood of the Port of Riga? It is operationalized in a number of specific ways, such as:

- What are the meanings and values attached to geographical surroundings and environment by different inhabitant groups?
- How important for them is the quality of air, water and landscape? What social characteristics define varying attitudes toward environmental change?
- What is the role of history and memory in human-environment relationship?
- What are narrative repertoires that people use to deal with environmental issues?
- What is the history and current situation with environmental governance and community activism in the port neighbourhoods?

2. The main characteristics of the survey

The objectives, design, and budget of the study determined that we chose an online non-probability survey instead of the desired probability sample survey¹. In addition, a number of representative surveys of Riga inhabitants and even residents of certain neighborhoods have been conducted so far, which have not been practically analyzed, and the secondary analysis of their data can also be used in this study. The data from these surveys can also serve as auxiliary variables for postsurvey adjustment for nonresponse bias. The 'Next to the Port' survey, on the other hand, can also be considered as an experimental or pilot nonprobability sample survey and can also be used as a model for analyzing the application of this method.

Target population: adult (18+) residents of five Riga neighborhoods (Bolderāja, Daugavgrīva, Mangaļsala, Kundziņsala and Vecmīlgrāvis). (see the Map 1 below)

Type of survey: non-probability sample online survey, the starting address of which is open and accessible to all. Respondents are controlled with filter questions (age, place of residence, etc.).

Survey tool: open source / code [LimeSurvey](#) (version 3.1.1.) software (Schmitz, 2018). Its main advantages are responsive and adaptive design, multilingual interface, filter and transition programming capabilities, as well as the ability to install it on your server, thus gaining more complete control over the tool and data.

Questionnaire: in two languages (Latvian and Russian) with ~50 questions (including ¼ of them as open-ended)².

The average completion time in minutes: 20 (mean), 15 (median), 12 (mode).³

Field work phase: 1st of April – Christmas, 2019.

Map 1. The territory of Riga's five studied neighborhoods (pink) and the borders of the City (red line) and the Freeport of Riga (black).

¹In fact, we would have to make five samples, one for each neighbourhood, and the fieldwork alone would “eat” about the annual project budget.

² Questionnaire structure *LimeSurvey* files as well as text versions with English translation are attached separately - <https://zenodo.org/record/3978130#.XzE0aCgzZPY> (see Daugavietis & Veisberga-Zīle, 2020).

³ Time for the completed questionnaire.

3. Survey preparation stage

The initial stage of forming the questions of the questionnaire was traditional – we defined the basic concepts and developed the main topics by following the research questions of the study. We also read theoretical literature and researched national and international surveys on similar topics in order to borrow and, if necessary, adapt questions from them. When analyzing the data obtained from the survey, reliable reference data will be needed for comparison and possible postsurvey adjustment, so we tried to make at least some of the questions the same as those used in other surveys, or to be easily harmonized.

When the first draft of the questionnaire was ready, it was evaluated by experts and activists from four neighborhood associations (“Kundziņsala”, “Bolderājas grupa”⁴, “Mangaļsalas iedzīvotāju biedrība”, “Vecmīlgrāvja attīstības biedrība”). Representatives of NGOs were kindly requested to indicate the variables that are of particular interest to them, as well as to add new ones if necessary. We asked the same for a high-ranking official of the Riga Municipal Development Department, as well as some experts in the field of environmental and sociological sciences.

After the second draft, the research group had to pick the prepared questions that should not be included in the final version of the questionnaire. Our goal was to try to fit within the 20-minute duration of the questionnaire. We chose this duration as critical based on the methodological literature and previous experience, taking into account not only that long questionnaires strongly increase the dropout level, but also that they initially reject potential respondents (Galesic & Bosnjak, 2009; Guo et al., 2016; Matjašić et al., 2018; Revilla & Ochoa, 2017; Vicente & Reis, 2010; Yan et al., 2011 etc.). In the introduction to the online questionnaire, we wrote: “[.] *it will take about 12-18 minutes to complete.*” We calculated the average time of completion of the completed questionnaires. The results are as follows (in minutes): 20 (mean), 15 (median), 12 (mode).

The created web form of questionnaire was also submitted for testing outside the project team. Representatives of neighborhood NGOs were also active at this stage, not only their content comments were important, but also corrections of grammatical errors in the language, especially in Russian. In Riga, the majority of the population belongs to the Russian-speaking community, so surveys, including this one, usually are conducted in two languages, Latvian and Russian.

In the end, we created four web questionnaires – one for each neighborhood (with its own unique URL), except for one for both the neighbouring Bolderāja and Daugavgrīva. Practically the only differences in the questionnaires were the wording of some questions and answers, such as those that mentioned the name of the neighborhood or its NGO. Word pronunciations in Latvian and Russian change in many cases, so we decided that it is easier to create a web form for each neighborhood than to try to program one universal one, although the *LimeSurvey* tool technically allows it.

4. The course of the survey

Since the starting address of our online questionnaires were available to anyone without restrictions, it can be called an unrestricted self-selected or even an open-access survey. At the beginning of the questionnaire, there were two filter questions – the respondent’s age (we did not survey those under 18) and place of residence (we were only interested in the residents of these five neighborhoods, or those individuals who often stay or visit these neighborhoods). However, we do not have reliable tools and indicators to monitor the responses of this anonymous survey, as well as the sample itself. As we clean the data, we can only use a few variables with paradata (such as the respondent’s IP address, date and time of completion of the questionnaire, time of

⁴ Bolderājas and Daugavgrīvas neighborhoods represents a single association.

completion of specific questions), as well as the answers themselves, assuming that most of the answers are true.

We published and advertised the links to the survey gradually, starting with the first survey of the smallest neighborhood (Kundziņšala). We also used communication channels of NGOs and local activists to disseminate the survey. However, the main and most important channel was Facebook. It is the most popular social network in Latvia, used by both main language communities – Latvian and Russian. Already at the beginning of the project, we had created a project Facebook website (<https://www.facebook.com/DziveLidzasOstai>), where we published links to surveys, adding promotional images and explanatory information (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. **Vecmīlgrāvis neighborhood survey advertisement for Facebook post**⁵.

We also advertised surveys in other ways. At the beginning of each neighborhood survey, we prepared a press release in two languages (Latvian and Russian), which simultaneously served both as a Facebook post text for the project page and as a text to be published in other online media. The response of other media was not great, and in fact the only ones who republished them a few times were the portals of Riga municipality. However, our Facebook posts were viewed and reposted quite a lot.⁶ They were also reposted in the most popular *Facebook* groups of the largest surveyed neighborhoods, each with more than 10,000 members – “Daugavgrīva / Bolderāja / Усть-Двинск / Болдерая” (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/dvinskcity>) and “Vecmilgravis” (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/vecmilgravis>).

We also invited the residents of the neighborhoods to participate in the survey in our public appearances – scientific or popular scientific lectures, interviews with the state and private mass media (radio, Internet portals). In order to promote the survey, we also wrote an article that was published in Latvian and Russian in one of the most popular Latvian Internet media, in which we have already analyzed and presented some of the results of the unfinished survey (Daugavietis, 2019a, 2019b). We also prepared a few hundred paper flyers (with an invitation to participate, with a survey URL and QR code) for advertising purposes, which were unsystematically distributed from hand to hand, as well as left in some public places (cafes, clinics, shops, etc.).

⁵ The author of the original visual design of the project is Marika Latsone. This is a modification by researchers.

⁶ The six posts directly related to the survey were viewed by between 1,000 and 10,000 unique users.

Figure 2. Design for the Kundziņsala neighborhood survey advertisement paper flyer.

We were aware that the non-probability sample internet survey of a large migration study implemented in Latvia was promoted via paid advertisement in the most popular Latvian internet media Delfi.lv with good success (Mieriņa, 2015). So we also tried this approach. Admittedly, the advertising costs and returns ratio was not satisfactory – the calculated “price” of one completed questionnaire was 17 euros (assuming that the Delfi.lv banner was the only recruitment channel in this period), which is already close to the price that would have to be paid for one completed questionnaire of a representative face-to-face survey.

Our experience with two Facebook advertising campaigns was much more successful, where we paid a total of about 50 euros. These campaigns yielded more than 400 completed questionnaires, and in this case one respondent’s “price” was ~10 eurocents.

Judging by the flashes of respondents’ activity, all the most important ones coincide with our communication and advertising initiatives: in April, we successively published survey posts and press releases; in the first and third weeks of May, we launched Facebook paid campaigns (in Latvian and Russian); in the third week of June, articles were published in popular Internet media; in October, we posted a message on Facebook about the imminent closure of the survey (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Respondents' activity by weeks (% of completed questionnaires [n=1143]).

As the quick acquisition of data was not our goal, and one of the tasks of using the survey was to address and involve the residents of the surveyed areas, we had planned an unconventionally long phase of the survey field work, to facilitate or democratize population participation. During the survey, we extended this period further, and in general they were $\frac{3}{4}$ a year. We started in the spring (we published the link to the first survey on April 1, 2019), but we closed access to the survey web form before Christmas of the same year.

Figure 4. Image of the latest call for the survey in Facebook ad (in Latvian).

From the point of view of the classical probability survey methodology, this is an undesirable and risky practice, as the data obtained during different times may prove difficult to compare. Public opinion can change rapidly, for example, in the event of an environmental accident or even a catastrophe. It seems that nothing so critical has happened in the course of our field work, either in the environmental, or in the economic and social field, although the fact that a disproportionate number of respondents from Mangaļsala took part in the survey during the last week of October could prove it.

Initially, we thought that the survey could be carried out in three modes: in addition to CAWI (computer assisted web interview), also CATI (computer assisted telephone interview) and PAPI (paper-and-pencil personal interview), knowing that certain groups of the population are harder to reach, such as seniors. In the introduction to the online interview, as well as in the press releases of the survey, it was mentioned that we are ready to interview the population also by phone, indicating the mobile phone number and e-mail address to apply for such interviews. Virtually no one applied. We also did not devote systematic work and resources to PAPI, so this way we gained only a dozen respondents (mostly by meeting with neighborhood activists or by interviewing residents with semi-structured interview or life story methods).

5. Obtained data

5.1. Quantitative data

In total, 2251 respondents took part in the survey, at least by using the survey link and opening the first page of the questionnaire. At least part of the demographic questions (they were placed at the beginning of the questionnaire) were filled by 1580, and 1143 respondents completed the survey. For a volunteer sample online survey, this dropout level (49%) is considered very low, especially given that the questionnaire had ~50 questions (including ¼ open-ended questions), as

well as some matrix-type questions, which are other factors which reduce completion rates (Liu, 2017; Liu & Wronski, 2018).

With the help of the survey we obtained the answers of 3% of the adults of the largest neighborhoods (Bolderāja, Daugavgrīva, Vecmīlgrāvis) and 11% of the adults of the smaller neighborhoods (Kundziņsala, Mangaļsala) (see the Figure 5 “Proportion of the population of the five surveyed neighborhoods,%”). In this case, it is not possible to speak of a response rate in the classical sense, because not every resident of these neighborhoods was personally invited to the survey and it is not possible to know how many of them had seen the news about the survey on their Facebook list, e-mail or other media.

Figure 5. **Proportion of the surveyed population of the five neighborhoods,%.**

Preliminary analysis of the data shows that the achieved sample in some socio-demographic indicators differs greatly from the target population (adult population of five neighborhoods). Its differences are typical for Internet surveys in Latvia – disproportionately many people with higher education, women, but disproportionately few – seniors and young people, as well as men (Daugavietis, 2015; Daugavietis & Eglāja-Kristsons, 2020). These and other differences between the sample and the target population may be attempted to be corrected by weighting or other postsurvey adjustment methods to verify that the data are generalizable. The necessary statistical data on the population of the neighborhoods are available from the Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia. It is also possible to use auxiliary variables for weighting, taking data from similar surveys as a benchmark.

5.2. Qualitative data

Of the approximately 50⁷ survey questions, one fourth were open-ended questions. Both those that are an explanation or a direct follow-up to a ‘quantitative question’ asked above and those that are not directly related to other questions. Online self-administered surveys have some advantages in the case of open-ended questions, for example, the respondents write down the answers themselves, they don’t have to hurry and think about the influence of the interviewer. This survey showed that it can be a good tool for asking open-ended questions.

For example, to the open question “*What do you like [in the neighborhood]?*” 85% of respondents who have completed the survey have responded. To the question “*In your opinion, what are the most important events in the history of [the neighborhood] (ancient or recent, important to many or*

⁷ Depending on the respondent's answers, he or she may or may not be asked additional questions (this is automatically provided by programmed filters and transitions).

only to you)?” – 66%; “In your opinion, which issues for the [neighborhood] society should be addressed first?” – 48%. It should be noted that none of these questions were set as mandatory in the survey web form.

If we evaluate the ‘quality’ of these and other open answers, by which in this case we understand how relevant and detailed the answers are, then there is a clear tendency – the longer the answer the researchers intend to receive from the respondent, the higher the item nonresponse, and the answers are of ‘lower quality’. For example, to the question “Maybe you have a story about [the neighborhood]?” 41% of the respondents answered (by writing something with free text), but there were only a few answers that could be classified as ‘stories’ by the project team members from the humanities. It should be noted that the online survey, which is (or looks like) a traditional quantitative data survey and has a relatively large number of questions, most of which are closed, respondents are not ready to answer in free text in length and detail.

Conclusions

The questionnaire was developed jointly by a project team made up of representatives from the social, humanities and environmental sciences. NGOs from the surveyed neighborhoods were also involved in this process. The final version of the questionnaire included an unusual number of open-ended questions (¼ of all), and preliminary analysis shows that the item response to them was good.

The fieldwork of the survey was unusually long – the online questionnaire was available almost for nine months. This was due to the specifics of the action research approach and the resulting desire to grant participation for as many people as possible, so the survey actually served also as a communication tool to communicate with the target community. With the help of the survey, we reached at least 3% of the residents of the largest neighborhoods (i.e. this proportion of the residents of the neighborhood participated in the survey), and 11% – the smallest.

At the time of writing this report, the data have not yet been properly cleaned and analyzed.

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Data and information about the project ‘Living Next to the Port’

<https://www.facebook.com/DziveLidzasOstai>
<http://lulfmi.lv/Dzive-lidzas-ostai>
<http://lulfmi.lv/en/Living-Next-to-the-Port> [EN]
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